

Enhancing the Quantitative Assessment of Ct Lung Nodule Using Morphometric Approach

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Abstract. Early detection of cancerous lung tumor has a greater influence in increasing the life expectancy and even in the prognostic aspects. The challenges associated with the diagnosis of the tumor is all the more complicated when the tumor is attached to blood vessels or lung wall. Identification of size of the tumor also has its role in staging and prognosis of lung cancer. Medical image processing is certainly crucial approach in improving the accuracy of the diagnosis. Considering the importance of aiming at accurate image analysis and immense complex data volume in medical image analysis, benefits of the cooperation of different complementary approaches is appreciable. In this paper a hybrid model of segmentation using k-means clustering with Morphological operation is proposed. A comparative based study on the sequence of the process implemented is presented which extends its scope in volumetric quantification of lung tumors.

Keywords: Segmentation, k-means clustering, Morphological operation.

1 Introduction

Among the cancer related deaths around the world, the deaths due to lung cancer is one of the major concern. Lung cancer which is categorized as Small Cell Lung Cancer and Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer accounts to a share of 87%. In spite of sophisticated imaging technologies, imaging methodologies the chances of increasing the life expectancy is very bleak, scaling to around 15 % [1]. This situation extends a scope for perseverant improvement in methodologies to detect lung tumors at an early stage. With many existing modalities for lung cancer prediction, the first level of commonly used method is the chest x-ray. However, CT scan is considered to be the modality of choice. Despite the improvement in MRI, with soft tissue scan and the movement of lungs, the challenge prevails [2]. Considering the importance of aiming at accurate image analysis and immense complex data volume in medical image analysis, benefits of the cooperation of different complementary approaches is appreciable. Attributing to huge volume of data especially in medical diagnosis, the Computer Aided Diagnosis supports diagnostic radiology and medical imaging [3]. While variation with biological aspects and pathological aspects introduce uncertainties to

medical image processing, it still serves as a crucial approach in improving the accuracy of the diagnosis.

The process of Segmentation is an important step in image processing which results in non-intersecting partitions exhibiting homogeneity and the partitions are heterogeneous by themselves. According to N.R pal and S.K Pal [4], there is no single method which can be considered as an universal approach for dealing with segmentation for all kinds of images. In this paper a strategy of segmentation on lung cancer images is presented which fuses k-means clustering and morphological operations prompting to serve as a methodology for volumetric analysis of lung tumors. This approach yields substantial PSNR value

The choice K –means clustering for segmentation in this paper is justified, as K means requires less computation time when compared to other algorithms. However, the selection in the value of K and initial centroids do pose as challenge in the usage of k-mean algorithm. Many researches have targeted this flaw in the k-means algorithm and have proposed the hybrid model or enhanced version of k-means [5] [6].

Structural properties of the lung lesions are enhanced by using mathematical morphological operation which treats images as sets. The principle of the morphological operations is related to the sliding of the defined kernel over the image of consideration [7]. In our work we focus on the volumetric analysis of the contouring action of the kernel used [8]. Emphasizing the importance of validations and metrics in measuring the results of medical image processing is crucial [9], the fact that a method must not deteriorate the interpretation capability is upheld. In our work we use PSNR to compare the results of the case study done.

2 Related work

Computed Tomography serves as the standard for pulmonary structures and surrounding anatomy for most of the diagnoses. The predecessor for the success of diagnose associated with CT scans lies with effective segmentation. Segmentation of lung CT images extends scope to Quantitative Computed Tomography in densitometry [10], Lesion detection for diagnosis [11-14], to staging of lesion [15, 16] for prognostic work.

Computer assisted segmentation in general can be classified based on many criteria. According to Matthew S. Brown [17], the pixel based segmentation involves various facts of contouring, thresholding etc. It can be better guided by knowledge based methods which use implicit knowledge with an intention of increasing robustness and automation. Considering the pixel based segmentation, clustering is one of them. Segmentation aims at creating partitions exhibiting homogeneity and one of the approach in finding the homogeneity or similarity of characteristics is

clustering [18]. Clustering helps in finding the relationship between data points so they can be segmented. Most of the algorithms in clustering use concept of distance, to measure similarity [19]. While high scalability and efficiency are the reasons for the usage of partitional clustering in many pattern recognition application, k-means clustering has a setback in handling categorical data [20]. However, k-means clustering is used as an effective approach in segmentation [21, 22]. The efficiency of K-means algorithm in segmentation partially relates to the choice of no. of clusters and the initialization of the centroid [23]. Madhu yedla et.al in their work [24] have proposed an enhanced k-mean approach in which better initial centroids are found by transforming the negative value attributes to the positive space and claims to execute the assignment of data points to relevant cluster in an efficient way. With k-mean having high value of K, the time complexity is high as many clusters are resulted and in vice versa case, the segmentation may not be a complete one. In case of images, the choice of the number of cluster is based on the histogram, [25] where, the relation between the image gray level distribution and histograms is considered and Otsu's thresholding is considered for addressing the randomness of initial cluster centers. K-means technique is reformulated [26] to make the method less sensitive to initialization of the centers by adopting ranked set sampling. The ranked set sampling uses the combination of simple random sampling under probabilistic sampling design and k-means. The role of segmentation has its implication in prediction of tumor contour, position, and volume for diagnostic and prognostic purposes.

K means clustering has been used in combination with other techniques for contour detection which in turn aides in volumetric quantification. The diagnosis and recovery of lung tumor is influenced by accurate volumetric analysis. Kavita et.al [27] in their work has proposed a framework for Accurate Segmentation and Classification of lung tumors. Segmentation is done using k means and classification is considered based on TNM. The nodules attached to the walls of the lungs are challenging from diagnostic perspective as most of the time they get overlooked by the CAD system. Multilevel processing has to be implemented to capture the nodule required for volumetric analysis M Javid et. al. [28] have chosen K means clustering and morphological operation in candidate nodule selection and segmentation

3 Proposed work

In this paper we use K-means clustering algorithm for image segmentation and morphological operations, erosion and dilation in smoothening of the segmented image. With this approach a case study is carried out in comparing the PSNR value obtained. The comparative study of this process is performed considering two cases, i). Using K-means segmentation prior to Morphological operation and ii). carrying out k-means segmentation after Morphological operation. On comparing the results of both the cases Morphological operation being performed post segmentation has yielded a better PSNR value. The approach serves as the base for using this strategy for effective volumetric quantification of lung tumors. The choice K-means clustering for segmentation in this

paper is justified, as K means requires less computation time when compared to other algorithms like Fuzzy-c means. Considering its speed and simplicity, 100 iterations are performed by parameterizing the accuracy required. Defining number of clusters is a prime thing in k-means clustering, here the segmentation results in 3 clusters which is defined in advance.

3.1 K-means clustering

Among Feature space clustering algorithms, K-means clustering algorithm is widely used. The algorithm creates partitions or clusters by grouping the objects based on similarity. The similarity calculation is based on the distance calculation between the objects. The similarity and the distance shows an inverse relation between each other.

The steps of the algorithm are listed below:

Step1: From the overall N categories, K clusters are arbitrarily selected as cluster centers

Step2: Distance to each cluster center for each other category is calculated and the category is classified as the nearest cluster center.

Step3: Recompute the cluster centers of every class that have been segregated

Step4: Repeat through steps (2) to (3) till the new center is less than or equal to the specified threshold, and the algorithm terminates

Considering that there are M data points in total, they have to be divided into k clusters. The K-means clustering aims at minimizing E

$$E = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^K \|x_m - b_k\|^2 \alpha_{mk} \quad (1)$$

Here according to the equation the parameter E is minimized if the data points are grouped to the closest center i.e.

$$\|x_m - b_k\|^2 \text{ Should possess minimum value as it measures the distance}$$

When data point m is classified into cluster (k), then,

$$\alpha_{mk} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \|x_m - b_k\| = \min_j \|x_m - b_j\| \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Firstly, we need to settle with the value of b_k and select optimal α_{mk} , later we need to fix α_{mk} and find the best b_k . The derivative of E wrt b_k tends the derivative to 0. With the smallest value of E α_{mk} is as below

$$b_k = \frac{\sum_m \alpha_{mk} x_m}{\sum_m \alpha_{mk}} \quad (3)$$

b_k , represents the mean of all data points in the cluster. The k means is bound to converge during every iteration by reducing the value of E

3.2 Morphological operations

Morphological Operation are few of the simplest operations which impacts the shape of the object, particularly closed shape. One of the promising application of morphological application is the contour detection. Its usage is endorsed in medical imaging with the scope extending to volumetric analysis of ROI. In our proposed case study after extracting the ROI from the preprocessed image through k –means clustering, the image is subjected to morphological operation of erosion n dilation. In the process, the kernel which is also referred to as the Structure Element (SE) is made to slide over the image

In the process of sliding the defined SE over the image, the pixel value of the image within the SE is equated to 1, else it is 0. Setting of the size of the SE depends on the requirement, in our proposed method, the size of eroding as well as dilating kernel is set to 5 as a result of trial and error. Mathematically, erosion, for a gray-scale image (x, y) , with kernel $k(s, d)$, which shrinks the foreground image, is defined as

$$(F \ominus K)(x, y) = \min\{F(x + s, y + d) - k(s, d)\} \quad (4)$$

To increase the size of the foreground object, dilation is used. Here any pixel value inside the SE is “1” depends on the value of pixel being “1” in the original image, given by the equation

$$(F \oplus K)(x, y) = \max\{F(x - s, y - d) + k(s, d)\} \quad (5)$$

4 Experimental Result

In this section, comparison of the two cases i). Morphological operation after k-means clustering ii). Morphological operation performed before clustering is compared, using the PSNR metric. In the result obtained the procedure of implementing erosion and dilation after the k- mean clustering, have given an improved PSNR value. Which proves to be an effective approach in volumetric analysis of lung tumors

Fig. 1. Input Image

Fig. 2. Segmented Image

Fig. 3. Plot of dilation on case i). and case ii) v/s PSNR

Fig. 4. Plot of erosion on case i). and case ii) v/s PSNR

Conclusion

In this paper K-means clustering is used in the segmentation of CT lung images with ROI being the tumors. The morphological operations were cascaded to k-means clustering as a pre n post processing operation. The case was analyzed comparing it with PSNR, which showed that carrying out morphological operations yield better PSNR. The case serves as the base in adopting the methodology in contour detection for volumetric quantification of lung tumors. However, improvisation in k-means w.r.t selection of number of k value and initial k value can be considered. In case of Morphological operation improved kernel selection can yield promising result in volumetric analysis of lung tumors.

References

1. Purandare, Nilendu C., and Venkatesh Rangarajan. "Imaging of lung cancer: implications on staging and management." *The Indian journal of radiology & imaging* 25.2 (2015): 109

2. Laurent, François, Michel Montaudon, and O. Corneloup. "CT and MRI of lung cancer." *Respiration* 73.2 (2006): 133-142.
3. Doi, Kunio. "Computer-aided diagnosis in medical imaging: historical review, current status and future potential." *Computerized medical imaging and graphics* 31.4-5 (2007): 198-211
4. Pal, Nikhil R., and Sankar K. Pal. "A review on image segmentation techniques." *Pattern recognition* 26.9 (1993): 1277-1294
5. Ng, H. P., et al. "Medical image segmentation using k-means clustering and improved watershed algorithm." 2006 IEEE southwest symposium on image analysis and interpretation. IEEE, 2006
6. Sulaiman, Siti Noraini, and Nor Ashidi Mat Isa. "Adaptive fuzzy-K-means clustering algorithm for image segmentation." *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics* 56.4 (2010): 2661-2668
7. Firoz, Raihan, et al. "Medical image enhancement using morphological transformation." *Journal of Data Analysis and Information Processing* 4.1 (2016): 1-12
8. Natarajan, Prem, et al. "Tumor detection using threshold operation in MRI brain images." 2012 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Computing Research. IEEE, 2012
9. Jannin, Pierre, Elizabeth Krupinski, and Simon K. Warfield. "Validation in medical image processing." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 25.11 (2006): 1405-9
10. Kemerink, Gerrit J., et al. "On segmentation of lung parenchyma in quantitative computed tomography of the lung." *Medical Physics* 25.12 (1998): 2432-2439
11. Senthil Kumar, K., K. Venkatalakshmi, and K. Karthikeyan. "Lung cancer detection using image segmentation by means of various evolutionary algorithms." *Computational and mathematical methods in medicine* 2019 (2019).
12. Skourt, Brahim Ait, Abdelhamid El Hassani, and Aicha Majda. "Lung CT image segmentation using deep neural networks." *Procedia Computer Science* 127 (2018): 109-113.
13. Memon, Nisar Ahmed, Anwar Majid Mirza, and S. A. M. Gilani. "Segmentation of lungs from CT scan images for early diagnosis of lung cancer." *Proceedings of world academy of science, engineering and technology*. Vol. 14. 2006.
14. Helen, R., et al. "Segmentation of pulmonary parenchyma in CT lung images based on 2D Otsu optimized by PSO." 2011 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Electrical and Computer Technology. IEEE, 2011.
15. Bhakta, Rupak, and ABM Aowlad Hossain. "Lung Tumor Segmentation and Staging from CT Images Using Fast and Robust Fuzzy C-Means Clustering." *International Journal of Image, Graphics and Signal Processing* 12.1 (2020): 38.
16. Lavanya, M. "Lung cancer segmentation and diagnosis of lung cancer staging using MEM (modified expectation maximization) algorithm and artificial neural network fuzzy inference system (ANFIS)." 2018
17. Brown, Matthew S., et al. "Knowledge-based segmentation of thoracic computed tomography images for assessment of split lung function." *Medical physics* 27.3 (2000): 592-598
18. Abonyi, Janos, et al. "Fuzzy clustering based segmentation of time-series." *International Symposium on Intelligent Data Analysis*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2003
19. Masulli, Francesco, and Andrea Schenone. "A fuzzy clustering based segmentation system as support to diagnosis in medical imaging." *Artificial intelligence in medicine* 16.2 (1999): 129-147.
20. Salem, Semeh Ben, Sami Naouali, and Zied Chtourou. "A fast and effective partitional clustering algorithm for large categorical datasets using a k-means based approach." *Computers & Electrical Engineering* 68 (2018): 463-483
21. R. Gonzalez and R.Woods, *Digital Imaging Processing*, Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, USA, 2002.
22. E. Gose and R. Johnsonbaugh, *Pattern Recognition and Image Analysis*, Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA, 1996
23. Dhanachandra, Nameirakpam, Khumanthem Manglem, and Yambem Jina Chanu. "Image segmentation using K-means clustering algorithm and subtractive clustering algorithm." *Procedia Computer Science* 54 (2015): 764-771
24. Yedla, Madhu, Srinivasa Rao Pathakota, and T. M. Srinivasa. "Enhancing K-means clustering algorithm with improved initial center." *International Journal of computer science and information technologies* 1.2 (2010): 121-125

25. Yao, Hong, et al. "An improved K-means clustering algorithm for fish image segmentation." *Mathematical and Computer Modelling* 58.3-4 (2013): 790-798
26. Ayech, Mohamed Walid, and Djemel Ziou. "Segmentation of Terahertz imaging using k-means clustering based on ranked set sampling." *Expert Systems with Applications* 42.6 (2015): 2959-2974
27. Kavitha, M. S., J. Shanthini, and N. Karthikeyan. "Volumetric analysis framework for accurate segmentation and classification (VAF-ASC) of lung tumor from CT images." *Soft Computing* 24 (2020): 18489-18497
28. Javaid, Muzzamil, et al. "A novel approach to CAD system for the detection of lung nodules in CT images." *Computer methods and programs in biomedicine* 135 (2016): 125-139